

Electrical Conductance of Acetylcholine Halides and Perchlorate in Methanol at 25°

N. H. EL-HAMMAMY, A. A. HASANEIN, M. F. AMIRA and F. M. ABD EL-HALIM

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Alexandria University, Alexandria, A. R. E.

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The conductance data of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in methanol solution at 25° are presented. The data were analyzed using the Fuoss-Onsager equation to obtain the characteristic parameters: the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution Λ_0 , the closest distance of approach a° , and the association constant K_A . Depending on the anion solvation, association was found to increase with increasing anionic radius. The trend of K_A is discussed in the light of the solvent separated ion-pair model. The electrostatic Stokes' radii R^+ and R^- are calculated and their sum is compared with the value of a° .

It has been found recently that the dielectric constant of the medium plays a very important role concerning the behaviour of electrolytes in solution. Various factors may influence the dielectric constant of the medium in the immediate neighbourhood of an ion¹. It was found that in very dilute solutions the dielectric constant of the pure solvent is the proper value to use for the so-called 'limiting law'. Furthermore, it has been shown that changes of the dielectric constant of the medium are closely connected with the corresponding changes of the velocity of homogeneous reaction in solutions. An approach to a theoretical interpretation correlating the changes in medium and the simultaneous changes in the velocity of certain catalyzed reactions was reported².

The effect of solvent may be considered as being two fold (a) stabilize the pairs due to the hydrogen bond chains in the alcohol and (b) solvate anions by hydrogen bonding³ so that the expected K_A values may increase with anionic radius of salts with the same cation.

The participation of alcohols in the ion-pair formation equilibrium, therefore, should involve both steric and coulombic effects. On the basis of this approach, the structure modifications of the alcoholic polymers generated by the added solvents should result in a variable influence of the alcohol molecules on the ion-pair association of electrolytes.

Several 3-parameter equations^{4,5} and 4-parameter equations⁶⁻⁹ were suggested to illustrate the relation between K_A and a° and Λ_0 , all of which are based on the model of charged hard spheres in a dielectric continuum.

This paper reports measurements of the conductances of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in methanol at 25°. The possibility of applying Fuoss-Onsager 3-parameter equation for 1:1 associated electrolytes is studied. The solvent separated ion-

pairs model¹⁰ is used to analyze K_A . Finally, a comparison is made between the summation of Stokes' electrostatic radii and a° .

Experimental

Purification of acetylcholine salts: The bromide, iodide and perchlorate were recrystallised from ethyl alcohol. All acetylcholine salts were dried in vacuum over phosphoric pentoxide.

Purification of solvent:

Methanol (BDH, AnalaR) was kept in contact with molecular sieves (4A, BDH) for about 24 h with frequent shaking, then distilled and refluxed with AnalaR silver nitrate (AnalaR) for 24 h. It was refluxed again with magnesium turnings (AnalaR) for 24 h and then redistilled. Again, the distillate was kept in contact with activated alumina for 24 h with intermittent shaking and then distilled. In all the distillations a fractionating column was used and only the middle distillate (65.5°) was taken. Its measured properties are: density (25°) = 0.78657 g cm⁻³; viscosity (25°) = 0.54448 cp; dielectric constant value used reported¹¹; specific conductance = 1.6 - 3.9 × 10⁻⁷ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Conductance measurements: An Erlenmeyer conductivity cell with unplatinized electrodes was used. The cell constant 0.05443 ± 0.43% was determined from several conductivity runs at 25 ± 0.02° using KCl (AnalaR) recrystallized from conductivity water and dried at 120°. The Lind, Zwolenik and Fuoss equation was applied. Pye 11700 conductivity bridge was used for measuring the conductance of the solution at 5 k cycle sec⁻¹.

All solutions were prepared by weight reduced to vacuo. Salts were weighed (± 0.1 mg) by difference on a microbalance. Dilution was carried out successively into the cell by siphoning the solvent using a dispenser.

Results and Discussion

To analyze the data (Table 1), Fuoss-Onsager ⁴ conductance equation for 1 : 1 associated electrolytes was used in the form

$$\Delta = \Delta_0 - S(c\gamma)^{\frac{1}{2}} + Ec\gamma \log c\gamma + Jc\gamma - K_{AC}\gamma \Delta f^2 \dots (1)$$

where, $E = E_1 \Delta_0 - E_2$; $S = A \Delta_0 + B$; $J = \sigma_1 \Delta_0 + \sigma_2$; γ = the degree of dissociation, and f = the activity coefficient. $A, B, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, E_1,$ and E_2 are constants for a given experimental system⁴.

A preliminary value of Δ_0 was estimated from Δ vs $c^{\frac{1}{2}}$ plot. A compact representation of the data is shown in Fig. 1, in which the reduced conductance Δ/Δ_0 is plotted against $c^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

A more accurate value of Δ_0 was estimated from the application of Fuoss-Kraus-Shedlovsky (FKS) equation^{1,2}

$$1/\Delta S_{(z)} = 1/\Delta_0 - (c\Delta S_{(z)} f^2)/K_D \Delta_0^2 \dots (2)$$

where the Shedlovsky function $S_{(z)}$ has been tabulated by Daggett^{1,2}

$$Z = \alpha(c\Delta)^{1/2} / \Delta_0^{3/2}$$

and α is the limiting tangent and K_D the dissociation constant. The plot of $1/\Delta S_{(z)}$ vs $(c\Delta S_{(z)} f^2)$ gives $1/\Delta_0$ as intercept and $1/K_D \Delta_0^2$ as slope. Fig. 2 illustrates the FKS plots for the studied salts.

The true values of the parameters $\Delta_0, \alpha,$ and K_A were derived using equation (1) and starting by the values of Δ_0 which was obtained from equation (2). A Fortran IV computer program was used on a PDP 11/70 machine. The accuracies required in these computations are ± 0.02 for $\Delta_0, \pm 2$ for $J < 200,$

Fig. 1. $\frac{\Delta}{\Delta_0}$ Plots for acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in methanol at 25°.

± 5 for $J = 200 \rightarrow 1000,$ and ± 10 for $J > 1000.$ Fig. 3 shows the variation of α with $J,$ from which α can be determined by interpolation.

As seen from the small values of the standard deviation $\sigma_{\Delta},$ the used conductance equation (1) expresses all the experimental data. This indicates that the value of $J(c\gamma)^{3/2}$ term in the 4-parameter equations⁶⁻⁹ may be neglected.

Fig. 2. (FKS) Plots for acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in methanol at 25°.

Fig. 3. Variation of J with σ° in methanol at 25°.

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE OF ACETYLCHOLINE HALIDES AND PERCHLORATE IN METHANOL AT 25°

Acetylcholine chloride		Acetylcholine bromide	
10°C	Λ	10°C	Λ
equiv/l	ohm ⁻¹ equiv ⁻¹ cm ²	equiv/l	ohm ⁻¹ equiv ⁻¹ cm ²
33.090	80.583	32.172	82.825
24.283	83.104	27.040	84.200
19.187	84.722	20.827	86.824
16.002	85.792	14.724	89.098
13.724	86.664	11.486	90.580
11.972	87.251	9.415	91.679
9.685	88.401	7.949	92.523
8.129	89.069	6.347	98.541
6.943	89.746	5.267	94.217

Acetylcholine iodide		Acetylcholine perchlorate	
10°C	Λ	10°C	Λ
equiv/l	ohm ⁻¹ equiv ⁻¹ cm ²	equiv/l	ohm ⁻¹ equiv ⁻¹ cm ²
15.354	94.842	17.144	99.198
11.334	96.550	12.240	101.901
8.952	97.880	8.491	104.314
7.413	98.837	6.695	105.692
5.701	99.951	5.459	106.800
4.589	100.716	4.605	107.531
3.852	101.328	4.325	107.795
3.282	101.913	4.148	108.123
		3.457	108.760

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTIC PARAMETER FOR ACETYLCHOLINE HALIDES AND PERCHLORATE IN METHANOL AT 25° DERIVED FROM EQUATION (1)

Salt	Λ_0	J	σ°	K_A	σ_A
Acetylcholine-Cl	97.03	1754	5.00	11.68	0.081
Acetylcholine-Br	100.93	1963	5.52	27.38	0.061
Acetylcholine-I	107.09	2069	5.50	18.79	0.070
Acetylcholine-ClO ₄	114.82	2510	6.50	36.23	0.068

Table 2 reveals that the values of Λ_0 , J, σ° , and K_A increases with increasing size of the anion.

The trend of σ° shows that the solvation of anions of these salts in methanol follows a trend which differs from that in water, i.e. ClO₄⁻ > I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻ which agrees with the expected electrostatic

point of view. In the present case K_A increases with increasing size of anions. The gradual increase of σ° with increase of K_A can be attributed to the relative position of the anion with respect to the cation which may not be complete spherical¹⁴.

The conductance of quarternary ammonium salts was measured¹⁵ with different anions in methanol at 25°. It was found that the values of σ° follow the order I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻ and K_A the order, I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻. It was also found¹⁶ that the values of σ° for i-Am₃BuNBr are less than for i-Am₃BuNI while the values of K_A , I⁻ < ClO₄⁻ are smaller in iodide than in perchlorate. Our results are in agreement with these results.

The conductance measurement⁹ of some alkali perchlorates in water at 25° revealed that the extent of ionic association increased with increasing the cationic size for any anion. This behaviour was attributed as due to the effect of solvation on ion pairing.

It was shown that the pattern of ionic association of tetraalkyl ammonium salts in methanol at 25° did not exhibit the simple dependence upon ionic size as predicted by the electrostatic theory. The surprising feature was that, for a given cation, the association constant increased with increasing anion size. Table 3 shows that the results obtained follow the

TABLE 3—CONDUCTANCE PARAMETERS IN n-BUTANOL AT 25° CALCULATED FROM FUOSS-ONSAGER EQUATION

Salt	Λ_0	σ°	K_A
Bu ₄ NCl	15.41	5.2	620
Bu ₄ NBr	16.07	5.4	860
Bu ₄ NI	17.16	5.2	1180
Bu ₄ NClO ₄	19.06	5.7	2200

same pattern as manifested¹⁰ in the higher alcohol, butanol at 25°. The conductance of some alkali metal iodides was measured^{17,18} in methanol at 25°. It was found that the association constant increased with the increasing cation size in the order CsI > RbI > KI > NaI and was explained on the basis of assuming the formation of solvent separated ion-pairs.

The extent of ionic association was found to increase with increasing size of the anion and is discussed in terms of multiple-step association process¹⁰. The solvent separated ion-pairs model was used to analyze the trend of K_A and the results are contained in Table 4.

TABLE 4—ESTIMATED VALUES OF K_A AND U FOR ACETYLCHOLINE HALIDES AND PERCHLORATE IN METHANOL AT 25°

Salt	K_A	K_1	K_2	U
Acetylcholine-Cl	11.68	9.77	0.19	0.17477
Acetylcholine-Br	27.38	9.51	1.88	1.06709
Acetylcholine-I	18.79	9.51	0.97	0.68055
Acetylcholine-ClO ₄	36.23	9.72	2.73	1.31610

TABLE 5—CALCULATION OF THE RADIUS OF THE IONS IN METHANOL AT 25°

Salt	$\lambda^0 \eta^0$	λ^0	$\lambda^{\pm}$	Average $\lambda^{\pm}$	R^+	R^-	$(R^+ + R^-)$	a^0
Acetylcholine-Cl	0.2848	52.31	44.72	—	—	2.88	6.25	5.00
Acetylcholine-Br	0.3068	56.26	44.72	44.68	3.37	2.68	6.04	5.52
				± 0.12				
Acetylcholine-I	0.3392	62.30	44.79	—	—	2.42	5.78	5.50
Acetylcholine-ClO ₄	0.3831	70.35	44.46	—	—	2.14	5.51	6.50

It can be readily seen from Table 4 that K_A , except for the iodide, increases as the anionic size increases, *i.e.*, the formed ion pair prefers the more desolvated form than the completely solvated one. It may be concluded that the orientation of solvent molecules surrounding the ion are disturbed rapidly for large anions.

The previous conclusion can be supported by applying the equation¹⁹

$$\ln K_A = \ln(4\pi N a^{*3}/3000) + e^2/a^0 DKT + U \dots (3)$$

where, U can be calculated from the following relation

$$U = \Delta S/K - ES/KT \dots (4)$$

in which $\Delta S/K$ is the entropy/Boltzmann constant ratio which illustrates the probability of the orientation of solvent molecules around free ions, and ES/KT is an energy relationship which includes the energy of the solvent molecules with respect to the two free ions and to the pair which they can make. The last column in Table 4 shows that U calculated from equation (4) increases slowly as the anionic size increases *i.e.*, the factor responsible for entropy change increases.

Radius of ions: The electrostatic Stokes' radii R^+ and R^- are given by the equation

$$R^+ = 0.8194 \times 10^{-8} / \lambda^{\pm} \eta^0 \text{ and}$$

$$R^- = 0.8194 \times 10^{-8} / \lambda^0 \eta^0 \dots (5)$$

In our case λ^0 was obtained from the intercept of the straight line (Fig. 4) which represents the relation between the Walden product $\Lambda_0 \eta^0$, and the reciprocal of the molecular weight as previously discussed²⁰.

To calculate $\lambda^{\pm}$ for [acetylcholine]⁺ the results of $\lambda^{\pm}$ for chloride, bromide, iodide, and perchlorate salts are calculated and the average value (Table 5) was used in the calculations. Applying equation (5) both R^+ and R^- may be obtained. The data are recorded in Table 5.

It can be seen from Table 5 that the values of a^0 are less than the summation of electrostatic radii of cation and anion in methanol. The values of the electrostatic radius of anion decreases with the increasing anionic size and follow the order $Cl^- > Br^- > I^- > ClO_4^-$.

The surprising low a^0 values from Stokes' radii for different salts in methanol are probably due to ion association²¹.

 Fig. 4. Evaluation of λ^0 in methanol at 25°.

It was found²² from conductance data and using the Stokes' equation that ions are smaller in water than in alcohols or acetone.

Conclusion: From the above results it can be concluded that the calculated a^0 values show that the solvation of studied anions follows the trend $ClO_4^- > I^- > Br^- > Cl^-$ which is expected from the electrostatic point of view. The values of K_A are found to increase with increasing anion size except for the iodide. From the solvent separated ion-pair model it can be concluded that the orientation of solvent molecules surrounding the ion is disturbed rapidly for large anions.

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